

UNDERSTANDING THE RISK PERCEPTION OF COVID-19 VACCINE AMONG ADULTS WITH COMORBIDITIES

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ABSTRACT

With the vaccination rollout in the Philippines to lessen the transmission and mitigate the effects of the virus during the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic in late 2019 up until 2022, Filipinos had different perceptions of vaccination. The study focused on understanding the risk perception of the COVID-19 vaccine among adults with comorbidities in Cagayan de Oro City. Despite limited previous studies that tackled the COVID-19 virus that was rampant during the commencement of this study, similar studies showed differences in how people perceived vaccination rollout during a major health crisis, e.g., Polio or influenza. The study used the Health Belief Model's constructs (perceived susceptibility, perceived severity, perceived barriers, perceived benefits, cues to action, and self-efficacy) in crafting a research instrument, a virtual in-depth interview, that aimed to identify the risk perception of the COVID-19 vaccine among respondents that had comorbidities in Cagayan de Oro. These respondents were identified through a snowball sampling method and the researchers used the data collected from the interviews to assess their risk perception of the vaccine. The themes that emerged from the transcriptions of the interviews were used for data analysis. The results indicate that the respondents had high perceived susceptibility, benefits, and severity. Unvaccinated respondents showed high self-efficacy for getting vaccinated. The various perceived barriers identified in this study against COVID-19 vaccination mainly include health issues, the effectiveness of the vaccine, and external influence. Finally, the respondents' cues to action are affected by their perceived severity, susceptibility, barriers, and benefits.

Keywords: *COVID-19, Vaccine, Virus, Pandemic, Risk Perception*

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic, declared by the World Health Organization on March 11, 2020, has become the most significant global health crisis since World War II. Caused by the novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2), COVID-19 is a highly contagious respiratory illness that poses a serious threat, particularly to individuals with weakened immune systems and underlying health conditions (UNDP, 2020; WHO, 2020).

In the Philippines, the first suspected case of COVID-19 was reported on January 22, 2020, with confirmed cases rapidly increasing thereafter. As of March 30, 2021, there were 731,000 confirmed cases nationwide, with Cagayan de Oro City reporting 4,089 confirmed cases and 126 active cases (Edrada et al., 2020; Sablad, 2021).

Throughout the pandemic, adherence to community and personal protective behaviors, such as mask-wearing, hand hygiene, and physical distancing, has been crucial for infection control (Heydari et al., 2021). Despite these measures, controlling the pandemic ultimately depends on the development and distribution of vaccines.

Vaccination has historically been a successful strategy in controlling infectious diseases. In response to COVID-19, numerous vaccines have been developed and rolled out globally. However, vaccine hesitancy remains a challenge, influenced by concerns regarding vaccine efficacy, safety, and misinformation (WHO, 2020; Dayrit et al., 2020; Cordero, 2021).

Understanding the risk perception of COVID-19 vaccines among vulnerable populations, such as those with underlying health conditions, is essential for effective vaccination strategies and pandemic control.

Research Questions

This study aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the risk perception of the respondents towards the vaccine?
 - a. Perceived susceptibility
 - b. Perceived severity
 - c. Perceived benefits
 - d. Perceived barriers
 - e. Cues to action
 - f. Self-efficacy
2. What are the factors that affect their cues to action?

METHODOLOGY

The researchers utilized the narrative research design, a qualitative research design equipped to explore and collect stories from an individual's experience and then shape them into discussions through an in-depth interview. With the study set during the COVID-19 pandemic, the researchers aimed to understand the risk perception of the COVID-19 vaccine among adults with comorbidities in Cagayan de Oro City. The study recruited adults aged 18-59 in Cagayan de Oro City with DOH-classified comorbidities (e.g., chronic respiratory disease) to explore the experiences of vaccinated and unvaccinated residents. Due to the high vaccination rate in Cagayan de Oro City, the study used snowball sampling to recruit 10 participants (5 vaccinated, 5 unvaccinated) from A3 Priority Group by reaching out to acquaintances, posting on Facebook, and asking identified respondents for referrals. Researchers conducted online in-depth interviews via Google Meet, utilizing validated open-ended and closed-ended questions to assess socio-demographics and COVID-19 vaccine risk perception (susceptibility, severity, benefits, barriers, cues to action, self-efficacy).

RESULTS

The findings from the interviews with participants about their knowledge, attitudes, and experiences regarding COVID-19 vaccines. The results are categorized into themes:

1. Knowledge of the COVID-19 vaccines
2. Sources of information
3. Perception of vaccine brands
4. Perceived benefits of COVID-19 vaccines (for vaccinated respondents only)
5. Role of vaccination in ending the pandemic
6. Experiences of respondents after being inoculated with COVID-19 vaccines
7. Assumptions of unvaccinated respondents regarding their experiences after being vaccinated

The results indicate a high level of self-efficacy among unvaccinated respondents regarding their plans to receive the COVID-19 vaccine. This self-efficacy is associated with their perceived benefits of vaccination, as they recognize the protective effects of the vaccine and its role in reducing the risk of infection. This finding is consistent with previous research, such as the study by Guidry et al. (2021), which found that high perceived benefits and self-efficacy are significant predictors of COVID-19 vaccine uptake intentions.

However, it is noteworthy that the supporting study did not specify whether its respondents were vaccinated or not, nor did it focus on adults with comorbidities. Therefore, our study suggests that future research should further explore the self-efficacy of unvaccinated respondents, particularly in the local context, to better understand their willingness to receive the vaccine.

Despite the unexpected outcome, as participants had previously cited concerns about vaccine effectiveness and potential side effects exacerbating their existing comorbidities, their high self-efficacy indicates a clear willingness to get vaccinated, especially if it provides protection against COVID-19. This underscores the perceived benefits of vaccination in reducing the risk of infection, as highlighted by the participants.

It is essential to acknowledge several limitations of our study. Firstly, while we gathered data from the A3 priority group (adults with comorbidities), we did not consider their specific comorbidities in our analysis due to privacy and sensitivity concerns. Secondly, the participants' perception of different vaccine brands was not explored, as our focus was on their overall risk perception of the COVID-19 vaccine. Lastly, our definition of perceived susceptibility did not directly relate to COVID-19 itself, as outlined by the Health Belief Model, which may have impacted our findings.

Despite these limitations, our findings have implications for government and health officials in designing and implementing vaccination promotion and education measures. Furthermore, our study provides a basis for future research to be replicated in other regions with high COVID-19 infection rates, exploring how participants' comorbidities and perceptions of different vaccine brands affect their willingness to get vaccinated.

DISCUSSION

The discussion section interprets the results and highlights key findings. It also explores the relationship between these findings and existing literature on COVID-19 vaccine hesitancy and acceptance. Additionally, the limitations of the study are acknowledged, and suggestions for future research are provided.

Knowledge of the COVID-19 vaccine

Having interviewed and transcribed the respondents' answers, their knowledge regarding the COVID-19 vaccine revealed two themes. These are: 1) mitigation of the effects of COVID-19 and 2) lowering the risk of infection.

Mitigation of the effects of COVID-19. The participants in the interview described the vaccines as something that mitigates the effects of COVID-19. They stated that the vaccines would only lessen the effect of COVID-19 if people were to be infected.

A vaccinated participant shared, "If ikaw tao na maturukan ana kung matakdan ka ana nga sakit, di kaayo inana kalala. It's more on the protection, maprotektahan ka from any critical nga mga situation." [It's for someone to not have severe effects when being infected. It's more about the protection that you are protected from critical situations.] Similarly, another participant who was a college student shared, "Ang vaccine gyud is magprotect gyud sa atoa diba from the virus itself. At least even if maigoan man ta sa COVID or sa virus, but still, dili gyud siya severe na igo sa atoa kay vaccinated naman ta." [Okay so first and foremost the vaccine really protects us from the virus itself. At least

even if we get infected with COVID or the virus, but still, it isn't as severe since we're already vaccinated.]

Lowering the risk of infection. The participants' view of the vaccines also includes their perception that the vaccines can lower the risk of getting infected with COVID-19. They understand that once you get vaccinated it doesn't mean that you do not get infected anymore and it does not guarantee absolute protection from the virus.

A high school teacher participant shared, “Para lang kini maghatag og protection nga dili ka matakdan deretso. So, dili man gyud siya makaingon nga prevention siya” [It is only to protect us to not getting easily infected (with COVID-19 virus) so I wouldn't call it something that prevents infection.] A college instructor also believed that the vaccine lessens the risk of infection and shared, “Dili guaranteed nga dili na jud ka mabalikan just like any other vaccine, mabalikan gihapon ka.” [It's not a guarantee that when you are vaccinated, you will not be infected again, just like any other vaccine. There is still a chance of being infected.]

Sources of information

The interviews with the participants revealed that they had different sources when it came to COVID-19 vaccine information, thus three themes were identified: 1) social media platforms, 2) Philippine government agencies, and 3) international healthcare organizations.

Social media platforms. The participants shared that one of their sources of information was social media outlets like Facebook. Social media sites offer a place where people receive information on different topics such as health and wellness.

A college student shared, “Mostly sa Facebook ug Youtube. Ug always pud ko gatan-aw sa daily updates sa COVID cases sa world.” [Mostly, from Facebook and YouTube. And I always watch the daily updates of COVID-19 around the world.] Another participant added that she only uses Facebook as her source of information regarding vaccines, “Facebook lang, through Facebook lang since kuan unvaccinated man ko so wala gyud ko nakakuha ug information gikan sa kuan gyud kanang gapang inject sa mga nurses.” [Facebook, only through Facebook since I am not vaccinated yet so I didn't receive information from what the nurses have injected.]

Philippine government agencies. Some participants also cited government agencies in the Philippines as their source of information for the vaccines, particularly the Department of Health (DOH). DOH released COVID-19 vaccine-related information during the initial stages of the pandemic.

One participant shared, “Like sa DOH, I always look at their websites, read sa ilahang mga articles like ipost regarding sa COVID-19 and sa vaccine.” [Like DOH, I always look at their websites, read their articles regarding COVID-19 and the vaccine.] Similarly, a female participant shared how DOH shares details about the vaccines, “Yes,

usually sad sa DOH since ilaha man gyud ginapresent ang every category or ang all about every vaccine. Diba so ang ilang effectivity. Asa sila gikan, asa sila nagorginate, giunsa ni siya pagbuhat.” [Yes, usually from DOH since they present every category or info about every vaccine. Also, their effectivity. Where they are from, their place of origin, and how they were made.]

International health agencies. Another source of information for the participants was international health agencies such as the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC).

A food technologist participant shared, “Ga-subscribe gyud ko anang mga article sa CDC (Center for Disease Control) in the US kay kini man gyud sila gastudy kung naa bay effect si food and ang mga bakuna.” [I subscribe to Center for Disease Control (CDC) articles in the US because they study the effects of certain foods or vaccines.]

Perception of vaccine brands

The transcription of the respondents’ answers gave an insight into their perception of COVID-19 vaccine brands. Four themes emerged from these: 1) awareness of geographical origin, (2) personal preference, (3) negative perception, and (4) friends’/family’s experience as the basis of the side effects.

Awareness of geographical origin. The respondents had a high awareness of the geographical origin of the vaccine brands. They were familiar with where the majority of the brands that were presented to them were produced. Vaccine brands such as Pfizer, Moderna, Sputnik V, and Sinovac were the ones that were most recognized in terms of their origin.

A college teacher shared this about Pfizer, “Daan naman pud ang Pfizer nga....naa na siya daan nga ngalan ba. Mas attractive siya sa mga tao nga magpa vaccine aside na US siya. Taas man gyud ang pananaw sa tao sa US pud.” [Pfizer is already a known name. It is more attractive to the people to get vaccinated aside from the fact it is from the US. People look up to the US.] For Moderna, one participant shared, “Mao pud na ang vaxx sa isa sa amoa diri. US based gyapon ang moderna.” [It’s also the vaxx of one of us here. Moderna is US based.]

Lastly, for Pfizer, a student shared this, “Honestly, when I heard Sinovac before because it is made in China, made in China gyud na siya (diha man gikan ang virus).” [Honestly, when I heard Sinovac before because it is made in China, it’s made in China (that’s where the virus came from).]

Personal preference. Among the vaccine brands presented to participants, there were those that most of the respondents preferred. These were the Pfizer and Moderna vaccines.

For Pfizer, this is what one of the respondents had to say, “I think most of us, or tanang tao sa world kay ganahan magpavaccine og Pfizer. Pfizer jud ilang first choice...” [I think most of us, or all the people in the world, prefer Pfizer. Our first choice is Pfizer...] Similarly, a tourism student shared the same thought about Pfizer, “For us opportunity jud namo na maka Pfizer or Moderna, kay among OJT kay maglarga mig international.” [Of course, in line with my course, because I’m a Tourism Management student and we have an online OJT. So of course, for us, it’s an opportunity if we get Pfizer or Moderna, since our OJT requires us to travel internationally.]

On the other hand, Moderna was also one of the options for a respondent. She shared, “Moderna is my second bet after Pfizer kay the same ra sila and being manufactured by a brand na reputable pharmaceutical company.” [Moderna is my second bet after Pfizer because they are the same being manufactured by a reputable pharmaceutical company.]

Negative perception. When presented with the vaccine brands, most of the participants had a negative perception of one of the vaccine brands. Most notably, the brand Sinovac received negative responses from the participants.

A food technologist participant shared, “First impression gyud nako about SINOVAC kay as a food technologist kay kahibawo jud mi na for one to develop a test na proven and tested - it will take many years gyud. In fact, five years dili pa gani na siya enough because it’s an emergency. SINOVAC was the first breakthrough nga gihimo gikan sa China. Daghan kaayo about sa kuan kay gikan sa China and 50% ra ang efficacy rate.” [My first impression about SINOVAC as a food technologist since we are aware that for one to develop a proven and tested test, it will take many years. Five years is not enough because it’s an emergency. SINOVAC was the first breakthrough from China. There are a lot of heresys since it’s from China and it has a 50% efficacy rate only.] One participant pointed out the casualties associated with the brand, “Based sa balita, mao man siguro na ang Sinovac nga daghan namatay.” [Based on the news, I think Sinovac is the one where many (recipients) died.]

Friends'/family's experience as the basis of the side effects. Tackling the side effects of the vaccines in the interviews revealed an idea of how most of the respondents relied on their friends’ and family’s experiences for the basis of side effects.

A vaccinated participant shared this about her asking her friend of the side effects of Astrazeneca, “Gipangutana nako siya kung unsay effect, parehas ra siya gyud daw gihapon kanang murag ka level daw sila sa Sinovac...I don’t know. Mao na siya akong nadunggan sa akong friends nga ang Astrazeneca is made in China so ka level ra siya medyo sa Sinovac” [She got injected with Astrazeneca in Cagayan. I asked my friend about the effects, it’s the same or like on the level of Sinovac...I don’t know. That’s what I heard from my friends that Astrazeneca is made in China so they have the same level as Sinovac.]

The results showed that the respondents have high perceived susceptibility as they are well aware of what advantage COVID-19 vaccines can provide for them. The perceived susceptibility of the respondents to COVID-19 vaccines is closely related to their perceived benefits as they implied that when seeking information about the vaccines, they gather information as to why the health action matters and ask the question of what good it can provide them. In addition, the results of the study showed that the perceived susceptibility of the respondents contributed to performing the desired health action. However, some of the available studies related to the study do not agree with this result. Specifically, a study stated in its result that perceived susceptibility has no direct contribution to why respondents perform the desired health action based on the findings of the study (Wong et al, 2021).

Moreover, the results revealed that the main sources of information for COVID-19 vaccines of the respondents are social media platforms, Philippine government agencies, and international health agencies. The respondents explicitly mentioned that they try to filter the information that they can get from these sources to get the bigger picture. Moreover, it is very important to know these sources because they contribute to the acceptance or refusal of health action. These sources can also be utilized for future interventions related to vaccination (El Elimat, 2021). With this, the researchers suggest that a new study is needed to explore more the direct relation of the mentioned sources of information with the risk perception of COVID-19 vaccines.

The results showed that aside from having a high perceived susceptibility to COVID-19 vaccines in general, the respondents had high perceived susceptibility as well to COVID-19 vaccine brands as they were aware of the origin of the vaccine. US-Origin vaccines are more preferred than any other country (Kawata & Nakabayashi, 2021).

The results of the study also showed that respondents prefer Pfizer and Moderna vaccines, while Sinovac received the most notable negative responses from the respondents. However, according to Del Castillo (2021), this should not be the case because instead of asking “Which brand is better”, one should ask “Which brand is accessible”.

Respondents shared that they had an idea of what the side effects of COVID-19 vaccines are from their friends/families. This could potentially mean that respondents trust those people whom they know compared to experts when it comes to experiences with COVID-19 vaccines. However, as the researchers could not find any study focusing on this result, the study suggests that this could be a great topic to begin a new research study.

Perceived benefits of COVID-19 vaccines

Three emerging themes came out as the perceived benefits of respondents who got inoculated based on what they had shared during data collection. These are: 1) protection against COVID-19 and its severity, 2) increase in self-confidence, and 3) perks when vaccinated.

Protection against COVID-19 and its severity. Most of the respondents believed that vaccination is a protection against the COVID-19 infection and its severity. Vaccines could help protect themselves and their loved ones from the virus. A college professor shared, “Number 1 is protection gyud. Mao gyud na ang the reason why we need to be vaccinated. Protection for myself, (and) for my loved ones, and for the people who will be meeting or encountering, nga ma-encounter nako.” [The first is protection. This is the reason why we need to be vaccinated. Protection for myself, (and) for my loved ones, and for the people who I will be meeting or encountering.]

Furthermore, other participants shared that this protection helps you and the people around you have a lower chance of getting infected with the virus.

A respondent who is a college student stated, “Kuan ma’am, for me kay dili man ata siguro gyud ingon nga makalikay ta sa COVID kay naa naman na siya. Pero at least kung mukuan ang COVID sa imo dili ra kaayo ingon nga grabe siguro ang epekto.” [Ma’am, for me, it does not necessarily mean that if (if you get vaccinated), we can avoid COVID-19 because it’s already there. But at least if (you get infected) with COVID-19, the effects of it won’t be that severe.]

Due to their unvaccinated status, other participants are still uncertain about the protection that the COVID-19 vaccines provide. However, according to what they read and heard, vaccination protects them from COVID-19.

A 52-year-old unvaccinated respondent shared, “Kung para sa akong kaugalingon, wala pa gyud koy ikatubag kung unsa ang benefits kay wala pa man ko nabakunahan ... Pero kung basehan nato ang claim sa DOH, makaprotect sa usa ka tao...” [For myself, I do not have any answer yet of what the benefits are, since I haven’t been vaccinated yet ... But if we base it on the claims of DOH, it can protect people...]

Furthermore, this protection can help people not to get hospitalized when being infected, especially when hospitals are congested with COVID-19 patients. A respondent shared, “So sa situation nato karon is, lisod man jud sad ang mga ospital labi na ang mga doctors ingana kay tungod sa kadaghan patients about COVID. Makahelp sad siguro siya sa kuan in a way nga malessen ang mga patients sa COVID.” [Our situation now is, that the hospitals are having a hard time, especially those doctors because there are so many patients with COVID. It can help in a way that it lessens the COVID patients.]

Increases confidence to adapt to the new normal. With the first benefit, the respondents shared how they see vaccines as protections against COVID-19 increasing their level of confidence and self-assurance for not getting infected with the virus. This helps them slowly adapt to the new normal, where they are confident to go out, buy necessities, travel, and the like.

A college student shared, “Having been vaccinated, when it comes to psychological aspect, confident ka, di na bitaw ka maparanoid na magadto sa gawas it’s because ‘ay I’m vaccinated na, akong kauban vaccinated na, so kung maigo mi, di lang

kaayo severe’.” [Having been vaccinated, when it comes to psychological, you are confident, and you are no longer paranoid about going outside because “I am vaccinated already, my companions are vaccinated already, so if we’re infected, it won’t be severe.”]

While most of the respondents shared that they are more confident now, some participants shared that despite this, one should still be careful and mindful when going out.

A 22-year-old college student stated, “For me kay di na kaayo ko hadlok ug medyo safe na ka from getting infected. Maskin safe gamay pero di gihapon magkompanyansa maskin nabakunahan na.” [For me, I won’t be that anxious and I’m a little safe from getting infected. Despite being a little safe, one should not disregard the danger of getting vaccinated.]

Perks when getting vaccinated. Some institutions provide perks for their customers who are fully vaccinated as a respondent shared, “Benefits are ... of course naa poy kanang maka percent off ka sa restaurants, sa magpadeliver ka, you just show your vaccine card. Flex ko lang. Daghan kay jud siyag benefits jud.” [Benefits are ... of course, there are discounts on restaurants, delivery services, you just show your vaccine card. Just flexing. There are a lot of benefits.]

Role of vaccination in ending the pandemic

The interviews with the respondents of the study and transcriptions showed the following themes as what they think the role of vaccination is in ending the pandemic. These three are: 1) lessens the transmission of COVID-19, 2) lets the economy go back to normal, and 3) lessens the congestion of COVID-19 patients in hospitals.

Lessens the transmission of COVID-19. Most of the respondents believed that the core of the importance of how vaccination in ending the pandemic is it lessens the transmission of COVID-19. One respondent stated, “...ug ang vaccine maga-help siya aron dili inana ka grabe ang transmission or pagtaas sa severe cases sa COVID...” [...and the vaccine will help to decrease the transmission or the severe cases of COVID...]

Another respondent shared the same perception on how vaccination can lessen the transmission and COVID-19, “...makahinay-hinay siya og wala sa pandemya tungod kay ang uban di naman matakdan. Kung tanan na mabakunahan, kinsa pa man ang matakdan? So safe na and mobalik na ta sa normal...” [...slowly it will solve the pandemic because others will not be infected. If all are vaccinated, who will be infected? So, it will be safe and we can go back to normal...]

Let the economy go back to normal. Aside from focusing on what people can benefit from the vaccines personally, some of the respondents shared how they can help a country go back to normal. One respondent specified that the Philippines should catch up with the nearby countries in advancing vaccination.

A college student shared, “Economy sa Philippines - kanang kailangan mo-catch up sa other countries especially nga nakarecover na sila by forwarding vaccination. Ang vaccine ang maga-protect para if maigo kay dili inana ka grabe gyud. Super beneficial para sa ako na PWD.” [For me, I won't be that anxious and I'm a little safe from getting infected. Despite being a little safe, one should not disregard the danger of getting vaccinated. The priority should be the people with the comorbidities because they need it. When it comes to the economy of the Philippines, we need to catch up with other countries, especially since they have recovered already by forwarding vaccination. The vaccine will protect us so that if we get infected, the effects will not be that worse. It's super beneficial for someone like me who is a PWD.]

Lessens congestion of COVID-19 patients in hospitals. Another benefit that the respondents shared is that vaccination, also, helps individuals recover from an infection faster, thus congestion in hospitals will be lessened. A participant shared, “Ang wards sa hospital kay loaded na so if vaccinated ka pwede ra ka maka-isolate sa inyong balay so dili na necessary moadto sa hospital.” [Hospital wards are getting congested so if you are vaccinated, you can isolate yourself in the comforts of your home.] This result was closely related to the mentioned benefits above which was that some of the respondents believed that vaccines can lessen the effect of the virus and risk of getting infected. Another reason why it could lessen the congestion of COVID-19 patients in hospitals was that when everyone is protected from COVID-19 because of vaccines, the transmission of it could be lessened also as mentioned previously.

Based on the results, the respondents have high perceived benefits from COVID-19 vaccines as the results showed that vaccination is a necessary health action during the pandemic. Specifically, the respondents explicitly mentioned that vaccines could not cure the virus, but they can only mitigate the effects of the virus and lessen the risk or chance of contracting it along with other advantages when vaccinated. A study entitled “Predicting intention to receive COVID-19 vaccine among the general population using the health belief model and the theory of planned behavior model” supported the results mentioned above as it concludes that among its respondents, the two perceived benefits prevailed were (a) vaccines prevent complications and (b) vaccines mitigate the risk of getting infected (Shmueli, 2021).

Moreover, most of the respondents implied that the perceived benefits of people with comorbidities outweigh their risk perception towards the vaccine as they decided to get vaccinated despite the negative things they heard, and as for the unvaccinated, the majority recognized the benefits of vaccination through the sources they identified. This finding is contrary to the results of a cross-sectional study entitled “Knowledge, attitude, and Acceptance of Healthcare Workers and the Public Regarding the COVID-19 Vaccine: a Cross-sectional Study” which showed that only a few people believe that the perceived benefits of people towards the vaccines outweigh their risk perception (Elhadi et. al., 2021). However, a result of another study entitled “Influenza vaccination uptake and Associated Factors among elderly population in Hong Kong: The Application of the Health Belief Model” supported the finding as it stated that perceived benefits of a certain number of respondents are the main reason for individuals to get vaccinated (Mo & Lau, 2015).

Experiences of respondents after being inoculated with COVID-19 vaccines

There are four emerging themes as the experiences of respondents after being inoculated with COVID-19 vaccines. These four are: 1) experienced common symptoms of flu, 2) varied reactions after being inoculated, 3) anxiety due to what might happen, and 4) triggered comorbidities resulting in severe side effects.

Experienced common symptoms of flu. Most respondents answered that they experienced the common symptoms of flu after being inoculated with COVID-19 vaccines. These symptoms were fever, loss of sense of taste and smell, body aches, headache, and the like.

One respondent shared that “With SINOVAC, nakuyawan kay ko ato kay, nawala akong panlasa, feverish ko and sakit kaayo akong abaga (murag bug-at) just like any flu vaccine. But after 24 hours ato, wala nako gihilantan ato pero medyo luya gamay.” [With SINOVAC, I was so anxious at that time because my sense of taste was gone, I was feverish, and my shoulders were in pain just like any flu vaccine. But after 24 hours, my fever was gone but I was still weak. Mostly for those inoculated with SINOVAC, their taste was gone. So, for three days I had no sense of taste aside from being feverish. They say that it was the effect if you had COVID and in my case, I was infected twice with COVID last year.]

Varied reactions after being inoculated. Some respondents shared that they had experienced much more severe side effects compared to those whom they knew were vaccinated as well. A respondent who got vaccinated at the same time as her father shared that “...Mao lang gyud to akong nafeel, fear nga unsa ang effect sa akoo, since I know some na J&J na walay side effects, while how come grabe ang side effects sa akoo...” [...That's what I felt. The effect is that fear since I know for some that J&J has no side effects, while how come to my side effects were that severe...]

She added that, “Mas okay sa akong papa na wala siyay nakuan bitaw (nabatian na side effects). Naa sa iyang mindset ‘Ah okay ang vaccine sa akoo. Compatible sa akong body ang vaccine since wala ra kaayo adverse effects’, and dili pud kaayo grabe ang effect sa iyaha. So, I think wala ra kaayo sa akong papa mao nang naka question jud siya sa akoo why inadto kay lahi iyang naexperience.” [It was better for my father that he didn't (experience any side effects). It's in his mindest ‘The vaccine is okay for me, the vaccine is compatible with my body’, since there's not much adverse effects and it was not that severe. So, I think it's not really a big deal for my father. That's why he questioned me why I had that experience since he has a different experience.]

On the other hand, some respondents shared that their reactions varied based on whether it was their first or second jab. A respondent shared, “Ang akoo is first dose nako kanang wala kaayo koy na feel ang hawoy lang sa akong abaga, ana lang. Kanang numb. Pagka second dose nako after a month, didto na dayon...” [For me it is that during my first dose, I didn't feel anything, just a weakness on the shoulder, like that. Like numbness. During my second dose after a month, that is where it happened...]

Anxiety due to what might happen. As uncertain as they were of what might happen, respondents shared that they felt anxious after getting inoculated with COVID-19 vaccines. A respondent shared, "Fear. Fear gyud noh. Fear nga what if maunsa ko since grabe ang side effects sa akona like totally chilled jud ko whole body, nakita pa gyud nako akong kamot nga gashake jud siya even akong tiil. Anxiety pud also after days sa akong jab, if kung maexpose ko, is that basin paspas ang igo sa akona sa virus so mas grabe hinuon ang murag ang virus bitaw na magsulod sa akona, dili pa mafight sa akong immune system since gaprocess pa man ang vaccine sa akong immune system." [Fear. It's always the fear. Fear of what would happen to me since the side effects were severe like my whole body was chilled, I saw my hands trembling even my feet. Also, the anxiety days after my vaccination, if I am exposed, there's a tendency that get infected faster with the virus so it will be severe if the virus enters my body, my immune system can't fight the virus since the virus is still processing on my immune system.]

Triggered comorbidities resulting in severe side effects. Since all the respondents had comorbidities, it could not be avoided that there were instances in which their comorbidities were triggered resulting in severe side effects.

A respondent shared, "...Takig ug hilanat pero after a day or two kay naka-recover man pud kay basig pud tungod sa akong sakit na affected ang akong thyroid. Wala ko sa mood..." [...Feverish but after a day or two, I was able to recover because maybe it was caused by my comorbidity affecting my thyroid...]

Another respondent, also, shared, "After that, some of my co-teachers naa dinhi (some lang), okay raman mi actually pero naay mga duha or tulo nga nag absent sila kay tungod nag hilanat sila. Wala nakaya sailang lawas ang kuan ang ilahang kay tungod siguro kay high blood sila. Mao to sila ang time nga kanang gipa stay sa sila kay after diba pagpa vaccine mosaka imohang dugo so pagka vaccine so gipa stay siya ug nag hilanat na siya." [After that, some of my co-teachers who are here (some only), we are okay actually but there are two or three who did not present themselves because they were caught with fever. Their body didn't take the effects since I think they had high blood pressure. That's when at that time they advised her to stay since after getting vaccinated, they had to check your blood pressure so they let them stay and then she got a fever.]

Assumptions of unvaccinated respondents of their experiences after being vaccinated

The transcription of the interviews with the respondents of this study showed two themes as the assumptions of unvaccinated respondents of the experiences if you get yourself vaccinated. These are: 1) variations of reactions on COVID-19 vaccines and 2) triggered comorbidities that may cause complications or deaths.

Variations of reactions on COVID-19 vaccines. Despite not being vaccinated, a respondent shared that not everyone shares the same reactions to the vaccines. Some were compatible while others were not. One respondent specifically said, "Sa akong pagtan-aw, mobalik na pud ta sa reality na dili tanang lawas sa tao kay parehas. Kay ang

tao nga hiyang sa bakuna nga gitupok sa iya, walay adverse effects - mga mild lang siguro (katulgon, labad ulo) pero dili siya severe. Naa koy igsoon na pastor, na aduna siyay mga miyembro nga namatay.” [For me, we’ll go back to the reality that not everyone’s the same. Because people who are attuned with the vaccine will not experience adverse effects or mild only (like dizziness and headache) but not that severe, I have a sibling who is a pastor and he had a member who died.]

On the other hand, according to some unvaccinated respondents, they heard that some people experience severe side effects after being inoculated with COVID-19 vaccines.

A respondent shared, "Na-mention naman nako ang uban no like sa katong sa Astrazeneca nay reports sa nag clotting, naay pag taas sa blood pressure, normal na hilantan, kato siya rare lang to mag lisod ug ginhawa. Common pud na side effect is mag allergy." [I've mentioned some before like AstraZeneca where there are reports of clotting, there's high blood pressure, normal fever, and difficulty breathing which is rare. Allergies are also a common side effect.]

Another respondent stated that from what they heard, one's reaction towards the vaccine depends on one's immune system, "Based sa akong mga kaila, kuan hilantanon tapos hawoy daw kuno ilang bukton. Ingana pero depende lang man daw kuno sa imong immune system kung kuan kag immune system." [Based on people I know; you experience fever and arm fatigue. It depends on your immune system.]

Triggered comorbidities that may cause complications or deaths. With their comorbidities, they were very cautious about getting vaccinated. This was the reason why hearing or reading that some people with comorbidities experienced complications or others even died could not be avoided.

One respondent shared, "...naa man gyuy mga cheka dadto sa amoa nga kanang mga masakiton bitaw sila nga nagpa vaccine kay na worse ilang sakit so gakahadlok ko mao nga until now unvaccinated pako. Worse bitaw mamatay ko nga walay liwat diba no kahadlok ba gyud." [...since there are rumors in our place that those who are vaccinated are still prone to sickness, that their condition has worsened and I am afraid that's why until now, I am still unvaccinated. The worst is that I'll die without having a child and it's scary.]

With the results collected, the researchers saw that there is a high perceived severity among vaccinated and unvaccinated participants, in regards to getting inoculated with the COVID-19 vaccine. Perceived severity is an individual's knowledge of the risks of getting vaccinated. They have stated how the risk is of experiencing common symptoms of flu, varied reactions after being inoculated, anxiety due to what might happen, and triggered comorbidities resulting in severe side effects. Although some of these cases were claimed by people as a direct result of getting vaccinated, experts still suggest that people with comorbidities should be the priority for they are at a higher risk of contracting the COVID-19 virus. The result of the study can be supported by this study,

“The health belief model predicts vaccination intentions against COVID-19: A survey experiment approach”, where it indicates how individuals who feel threatened or perceive high levels of risk of COVID-19 disease will be more likely to express higher levels of intentions to vaccinate against COVID-19 (Zampetakis & Melas, 2021). With the high severity perceived among the participants, this can be correlated to their perceived benefits, as they have stated that when getting inoculated, has benefits, especially for an individual. Most of them are well aware of the vaccine’s effectiveness, especially on its side effects, but they still choose to get vaccinated as a means of protection and getting less risk of being infected with the virus. Some are still refusing, especially for those unvaccinated individuals, for the sake of how they perceive the vaccine as somewhat worsening their health condition.

Hindrances for vaccination

The participants who are vaccinated and unvaccinated have shared what the things are that could’ve hindered them from getting the vaccine. The researchers listed six themes: 1) effectiveness of the vaccine, 2) influence from other people, 3) health problems, 4) rumors or misinformation, 5) fear of the possibility of malpractice of the vaccine, and 6) process of vaccination.

Effectiveness of the vaccine. Some of the respondents stated that the effectiveness of the vaccine is one of the factors that could’ve prevented them from getting the vaccine. A college professor shared that one is because of the vaccine’s effectiveness and how it was made: “Actually, at first gyud, dili jud ko ganahan magpavaccine kay I know man gud no nga five years gali is not enough and ongoing pa ang testing so dili pa gyud siyas proven and tested.” [Actually, at first, I did not prefer to get vaccinated because I knew that even five years is not enough and clinical trials are still ongoing, so it’s not yet proven and tested.]

A Junior High School teacher shared that he got this fear of getting vaccinated due to the uncertainty of the vaccine. “Fear o kahadlok kay dili man gud ta sigurado. Dili ta sigurado kay halimbawa kung tupukan ta ani, kay bakunahan man ka deretso. Maayo unta kung ang gibuhad sa DOH kay skin tests sa ato ni unya pagkahuman og dili moreact ayha dayun para makapili asa nga brand nga gamiton. Dili siya laboratory tested na pamaagi. Dili pa gyud ni safe kay maghulat pa ta for two years ug sila na mismo nag-ingon ana. So, kung ingon ana nga maghulat pa ta og inana kadugay, so unsa man diay tong nabakunahan na so mura ra gihapon og gi-eksperimentohan sila.” [Fear due to uncertainty. We are uncertain if for example you are directly injected. It will be better that DOH should perform skin tests to verify if there is a reaction and if none, then we will proceed to choosing our preferred vaccine brand. It’s not a laboratory tested method. And it’s not yet safe because we need to wait for another two years as they say. So, if they say that we need to wait that long, is it safe to say that those who are vaccinated are mere experiments only?]

Stating how the vaccines can only be for an experiment, a 45-year-old teacher added how the vaccines are just experimental and were made for health crisis emergencies, “Mao na ang nakapapugong sa akua base sa ako pag basa kay clinical trial

man sad gyud and gi tagaan lang ang kana nga mga kompanya sa vaccine sa authority to administer aron pag sulbad sa health crisis emergency gyud siya na himuon pero dili nato malikayan ang truth na this is experimental.” [That is the one that prevented me from getting vaccination because based on what I have read is it just a clinical trial and the companies who made the vaccine were given authority to administer it so that they can help solve this health crisis emergency and that is where they are made of and we can't deny the truth that this is experimental.]

A tourism student shared the same sentiments, further stating the percentage and the risk vaccines imposed. “Dili gyud ko fully in trust kanang mga vaccine kay diba they explained and makitan pud nimo pila kapercent nga mga vaccine and kanang mga risky.” [I don't have that full trust in the vaccine since they explained and you can see its percentage and its risk.]

In contrast with their statements, an education major student shared no hesitations when it came to getting vaccinated, stating the effectiveness, benefits, and side effects. “To be honest pag abot na sa vaxx, gusto na gyud kay ko magpabakuna. Even though layo pa kay ko sa kuan, I don't have fear on unsay side effect sa kuan. Basta ang ako ra is gusto nako magpabakuna for the safety of everyone around me gyud. So, I think wala gyud nagkuan jud sa ako na dapat dili ko magpavaccine.” [To be honest, when it comes to vaccines, I want to get vaccinated. Even though I am still far from that, I don't have a fear of its side effects. The only thing that I want is to get vaccinated for the safety of everyone around me. I think it didn't occur to me that I shouldn't get vaccinated.]

Influence from other people. Some of the respondents shared that the influence coming from their peers or family members might be their factor in not getting inoculated with the vaccine. The college professor mentioned another factor, the influence of her workmates, “Daghan kaayo ko friends, mostly food technologists, nga ayaw sa....” [I have a lot of friends, mostly food technologists, saying to not yet get vaccinated...]

But eventually, the influence from the medical frontliners made her get vaccinated for protection, fighting that fear of her factors, “...pero nakita man nako nga ang mga medical frontliners, nagpavaccine naman. So, kung nagpavaccine sila, meaning nituo si medical frontliners, yes na lang ko kay ako man gud I want to be protected man. So wala na to ang fears nga di na ko magpavaccine.” [but I have seen medical frontliners getting vaccinated. So, if they were vaccinated, that means medical frontliners believe in it, so I said yes because I want to be protected.]

Furthermore, a guidance counselor shared that her parents, who are Senior Citizens, are among the factors that influence her not to get any vaccinations. “And then second ang makababag sa akona is katong...kana laging ang akong mama ug papa gyud, usa gyud na (audio not clear) kay daghan kay siyag i-share sa akona about sa vaccine (audio not heard) vaccine naa daw kuno'y namatay so ako nga iyang anak, nahadlok pud ko kay....” [And then second that hindered me is that...my mother and father, they are one (audio not heard) because they shared a lot on me about the vaccine (audio not heard) the vaccine is some people died so me as their daughter, I also got scared since...]

Health problems. In terms of health problems, most of them have shared that their health condition might be one of their factors, considering that they may be also prone to the virus and at the same time, may trigger due to its side effects. A college student has shared that one of the things that may prevent him from getting vaccinated is his health condition which he shared that he had previously undergone an operation with his existing condition. “Pero katong sa ako nga time kay gakahadluan ko kay gikan ko therapy and hina na akong immune system.” [But during my time, I was nervous because I had a therapy before that so my immune system was compromised.]

A participant in her 20s shared that it is due to her immune system. “Kuan ma’am ang isa sad sa problema is kanang akong immune system ba. Hinay sad ang akong immune system and murag mahadlok ko ma unsa ba uy.” [I think one of my problems, ma’am, is my immune system. My immune system is weak and I’m kind of scared of what would happen.]

Another college student also shared that it is due to her heart condition, “Since naa man koy sakit sa heart, mao na siya ang kining ga prevent sa akona nga magpabakuna kay diba like sa akong ga storya a while ago nga kuan kanang mga masakiton bitaw nga nagpabakuna kay nag worse ilang sakit so that thing, until now, maong unvaccinated ko.” [Since I have a heart disease, that’s the thing that prevented me from getting vaccinated. From what I’ve said a while ago about those who are prone to sickness is that their condition has become worse, so that’s why, until now, I am still unvaccinated.]

Moreover, one participant shared another factor of not getting vaccinated, which is his allergic reaction, “Pero sa ako lang na one sa akong gikahadluan kay kani gyud ang allergic reaction leading to breathing difficulty. Kung bata-bata pa siguro ko ug healthy, di gyud ko mahadlok anang mga bakuna.” [But for me one of the things I fear the most is this allergic reaction leading to breathing difficulty. If you’re younger and healthy, you don’t need to be afraid of getting vaccinated.]

About the previous respondent’s allergic reaction, another participant shared also that her onset of allergies caused her to not get any vaccination, as per her doctor’s advice. “Kung I-vaccine daw ko ato na time, kay kung suga pa daw (naka on ang switch sa suga), butangan pa daw akong lawas ug maka trigger sa allergy basig mag lain daw akong ginhawa. Mao to wala ko nidayon. Until this time, wala papud ko nagpa vaccine pud kay ako man gipaminiwan akong lawas kay ga balik-balik man gyud bisan gamay lang bitaw na katol-katol, kaning ma tiguwang wala man ko ani sauna.” [If I were to get vaccinated at that time, if it is like a switch (the switch is on), if there’s something to be put in my body that could trigger the allergy, it has the tendency that I will have difficulty breathing. That’s why I didn’t continue. Until this time, I didn’t get vaccinated since I am observing my body since it keeps on appearing even if it’s just a little bit itchy. Even in my old age, I didn’t have this before.]

An online seller shared that she has a lot of medication intake and the vaccine might trigger her existing condition, which is related to autoimmune disease, “Unya kuan mahadlok ko ba kay daghan baya ko gi take na tambal nya dili baya sila musaba nga

mao na ang epekto nga kuan so di nalang ko, I won't take risk, ba?" [I am afraid since I have so many medications and they won't say that this is the effect so I didn't, I won't take the risk, right?]

Rumors or misinformation. Some of the respondents have shared that it's because of rumors they heard or misinformation that they have read that could prevent them from vaccination. One participant has shared one of the factors that would not let her be able to vaccinate herself, which includes "memes" that are being shared on social media. "Tapos kana pud sa social media, ang mga memes. Grabe pud baya og himo og mga memes na makakuan sa mga tao, imbes gusto na sila magpavaccine, mubackward na pud sila." [And then on those social media, those memes. They keep on making memes that may affect those people, instead of wanting to get vaccinated, they'll have to go backward.]

When asked about the rumors she has heard about getting vaccinated, she also added: "Naa gyud toy rumors if kana tong navaccine sila, namatay sila." [There were rumors that if you were vaccinated, they died.]

In relation to misinformation, a participant shared that the social media that contains misinformation is also one of the things which feared her from getting vaccination. "...nahadlok pud ko kay (audio not heard) kay I have heard sa kanang sa Tiktok scroll-scroll ko. Sa una grabe kaayo ang pangdaot sa vaccine baya (audio not heard) naay mga nangamatay, tanan ba patay ana ko nga 'ha nganong mangkuan mani sila wala ko kasabot ngano mamatay man ang magpabakuna' so kana. Una gyud ang kahadlok sa kanang tungod sa mga misinformation mga inana." [...I also got scared since (audio not heard) I have heard from Tik Tok while scrolling. Before, there were some who degraded the vaccine (audio not heard) there were some who got dead, all of them who died and I was like 'Why are they like this? I don't even understand why they died after getting vaccinated' like that. First is the fear because of the misinformation around.]

Fear of the possibility of malpractice of the vaccine. One participant has shared that she also has that fear of getting vaccinated, that there is a possibility of getting jabbed wrongly. "One thing jud nga factor nga nakaprevent gyud ko adto ko get vaccinated is that ang kahadlok. Ana ang kahadlok. And dili pud ta adto sa zombie apologizes (zombie apocalypse). Basin nag paturok ba, basin masayop tapos ang sulod dayon adto sa vaccine." [One factor that prevented me from getting vaccinated is the fear. That is the fear. And not to the extent of turning into a zombie. Maybe if you get a jab, it might be wrongly injected, and what the vaccine contains.]

Process of vaccination. A participant shared what could be her another hindrance of not getting vaccination. One is a disorganized system of vaccination. "Unya lastly ang nakababag pud sa akua sa vaccine is walay klaro na system man gyud sa una (audio not heard) asa man gyud ko magpa register ani kanang muduol ba ko ana-ana dugay kaayo mao nang tungod sa ka-laay, dili nalang sa siguro ko murag ana ba (audio not heard) kanang ka dugay ba nga kanang mubalik nako sa Cabanglasan wala pa ko nabakunahan unya diri kay dapat pag abot nimo diri, fully vaccinated naka, inana bitaw

so unya ang kuan pagyud kay murag ako....ay kami pud katong before pa mi nag vacation, before we came back diri sa Cabanglasan, gi ignan man gyud mi nga “pagpaningkamot mo ug pagpabakuna” (audio not heard) fully vaccinated na ko nga “ha, dili diay ang school mangita ug way nga mabakunahan ang mga teachers?” so (audio not heard) “ay wala raman diay gihapon, mag hulat na pud dayon ta” kay kanang naa na sa akong mind ba nga ang systema sa Philippines, ang systema sa LGU, sa barangay, is wala, walay klaro.” [And lastly that hindered me from the vaccine is the system is not clear before (audio not heard) where should I register, should I go to this, like it took a long time and it’s because of the boredom, I don’t think I should continue, like that. Like, it took so long and I will be back in Cabanglasan and yet still haven’t vaccinated and here is that when you arrive, you should be fully vaccinated, like that and for me, for us before when we had our vacation, before we came back here in Cabanglasan, we were told “you should work hard with getting vaccinated.” (audio not heard) I am fully vaccinated that “ha, isn’t the school going to look for ways for the teachers to get vaccinated?” so (audio not heard) “ah so there’s no one, we still have to wait.” because it’s already on my mind that the system here in the Philippines, system in the LGU, in the barangay, is none, not clear.]

The results showed the vaccinated and unvaccinated participants’ barriers to getting vaccinated. Perceived barriers are the things or factors that inhibit them from getting inoculated with the vaccine. They have stated how the effectiveness of the vaccine itself is just one of the barriers that prevented them from getting vaccinated. Considering they belong to a group with comorbidity and despite having a different vaccination status, they still perceive the same barrier that could hinder them from getting inoculated. According to this study, “COVID-19 vaccine: A comprehensive status report”, it stated how the process of vaccine development is quite laborious with various stages, including the pre-clinical stage, and clinical development which is a three-phase process. However, if sufficient data is already available, it has been recommended to skip a few stages, to accelerate the attainment of a vaccine faster with a quick regulatory review, approval, manufacturing, and quality control. (Kaur & Gupta, 2020). However, the World Health Organization has also shared that all COVID-19 vaccines approved by WHO for emergency use listing have been through randomized clinical trials to test their quality, safety, and efficacy. To be approved, vaccines are required to have a high efficacy rate of 50% or above. After approval, they continue to be monitored for ongoing safety and effectiveness (WHO, 2021). With this, a study entitled “The use of the health belief model to assess predictors of intent to receive the COVID-19 vaccine and willingness to pay” supported the results with their discussion, stating that the perceived barriers that are found in their study and in other studies include worry about the side effects, efficacy, and safety of the vaccine. (Wong, et., al, 2020). Though this is an expected outcome for most of the respondents, they have stated that they are still uncertain about the effectiveness of the vaccine, considering they are still in a clinical trial phase and how it has quickly developed for over a year.

The participants have also mentioned that their health issues, such as their existing comorbidity, could be or hindrance to them concerning vaccination. Considering that they belong to the A3 Priority Group, this must take into consideration that the participants

make their health condition their utmost priority, as they have heard how the side effects that they could get when getting inoculated could trigger their existing health condition. Fear and anxiety are also associated among the participants since they have shared that the side effects may trigger their existing condition. The results somehow do not agree with other studies, as this study “COVID-19 vaccine hesitancy and related fears and anxiety” stated in their discussion that it seems plausible that fears that are directly related to the physical health of oneself or loved ones are associated with a higher acceptance of a vaccination that promises to reduce the probability of those negative outcomes. (Bendau et al., 2021). This suggests that future researchers explore more on the factors, such as their health problems, as their hindrance of not getting inoculated with the vaccine.

Another hindrance could be the external factor, which is the influence of peers and family members. As stated by this one participant, the parent’s influence may affect its decision to get inoculated or not. According to this one study, “Using Behavioral Insights to Increase Vaccination Policy Effectiveness”, it is stated that the involvement in the vaccination decision is high for parents who engage in subjective expected utility calculation. They engage in an extensive information search for the pros and cons of vaccination. These individuals do not have a strong pre-existing attitude toward vaccination but base their decisions on utility maximization, which leads to vaccination or non-vaccination, depending on the subjective evaluations of risks. (Betsch, et al., 2015). The result of this study shows how external influence is a big contributing factor to a participant’s decision to whether or not get vaccinated, especially if they have concerns about what they know about the vaccine that they could tell that participant. External influence is also a big factor, especially in vaccine information dissemination. This also suggests that future researchers to further explore those external influences of what could be the other factors such as their attitude towards vaccination that influences those people with comorbidities and their decision on the COVID-19 vaccine.

Promoting of vaccination

In this portion, the vaccinated respondents were asked if they recommend their family members and friends to get vaccinated. The researchers have listed the following themes: 1) recommend due to its benefits, 2) recommend due to their experience, and 3) recommend due to vulnerability.

Recommend due to its benefits. One participant has shared that she will recommend the vaccine to her family, specifically her parents who are Senior Citizens, for protection against the virus. “Yes, ako gyud number one gyud kay akong parents kay senior citizen man and then dili gyud unta sila kay SINOVAC lage pero ako lang gyud is protection lang gyud.” [Yes, I am the number one who recommends it to my parents, especially since they are senior citizens despite their hesitation because it’s SINOVAC but all I want is to protect them.]

Another participant added to what the previous respondent shared, stating it will protect yourself and the people around you. “Since being vaccinated gyud regardless of what side effect it could be, is dako gyud kay siyag benefit. Both sa carrier og sa other people or the people around you. Lahi ra jud siyag kuan bitaw. So, it is needed to recommend na ang other people to get vaccinated kay just for itself na ikaw mismo maprotektahan ka and the people around you.” [Since being vaccinated, regardless of what side effect it could be, has a big benefit. Both on the carrier or to the other people or the people around you. The feeling is just different. It is needed to recommend other people to get their vaccination because it's also for ourselves to get protected and those people around you.]

Moreover, another participant shared that to get vaccinated is to lessen their risk against the virus, that's why she will encourage especially those older ones. “Diba sabi nila dapat ang older ones is dili jud magpavaccine kay tigulang na. Basin pagpavaccine matigok. But for me, to get vaccinated is very helpful for them para sad maless gyud ilang risk.” [Since they say that those older ones should not get vaccinated since they are old. In case they'll die once vaccinated. But for me, getting vaccinated is very helpful for them to lessen their risk.]

Getting vaccinated is also building confidence within themselves. Another participant recommends the benefits of getting vaccinated. “And kanang also it builds up confidence jud to mingle with other people so by saying those nga akong naexperience and kanang why they should get vaccinated sa akong mga kaila na wala pa nagpavaccine, is that kanang as of now sa akong girecommend pud nako kay nagpavaccine na pud nuon sila. And they were happy bitaw with the effect or with the confidence na nagbuild sa ilaha after being vaccinated.” [It also builds up the confidence to mingle with other people so from saying those experiences and why they should get vaccinated, as of now what I recommend is they also get vaccinated. They were happy with the effect or with the confidence that they built after being vaccinated.]

Recommend due to their experience. Some of the participants have shared their experiences that made them recommend those people to get their vaccination. One participant shared that it is due to her mother's experience with COVID-19 that made not just him, but for his family, promote vaccination. “Usa ka rason nganong nagpavaccine mi kay akong mama nga naa sa Manila kay na-covid siya so that time nakathink mi kailangan jud magpavaccine.” [One of the reasons that we get ourselves vaccinated is that my mother in Manila got infected with COVID-19, so that time we think that it is necessary to get vaccinated.]

Another participant shared that she would recommend vaccination since she went through with it. “Of course. Nadaanan ko naman, I will recommend my family to get vaccinated.” [Of course. I already went through it, so I will recommend my family to get vaccinated.]

Recommend due to vulnerability. One participant has shared that she will recommend her family members, especially her parents who are Senior Citizens, to get

vaccinated since she thinks they are vulnerable to the virus. “Hangtod karon, gina encourage nako sila kay kanang luoy man gyud sila naka sige ingon ko sa ilaha na ‘kamo baya ang luoy kay Senior Citizen mo, fully vaccinated na mi ni kuya, kami ni ate, naay bata sa balay’ murag sila nalang tulo ba, akoang pagumangkon (audio not heard) grabe ka (said an expression) dili pa baya to sila pwede, so grabe among careful.” [Until now, I keep on encouraging them since they are the ones who I pity the most. I keep on telling them that “you’re the ones who’s vulnerable since you are already senior citizens, big brother and I are fully vaccinated, together with big sister, there are kids in this house” thinking they’re the three of them left, my niece (audio not heard) they are (said an expression) they aren’t allowed, so we are very more careful.]

Vaccination plans

This section is for those unvaccinated people and what are their plans when it comes to vaccination. They were asked if they consider themselves to get vaccinated and their thoughts about it. These were the following themes: 1) hesitant due to the efficacy of the vaccine, 2) vaccinating because it is mandated, 3) vaccinating if there’s no existing health condition, 4) considering but not yet fully decided, and 5) not vaccinating.

Hesitant due to the efficacy of the vaccine. One participant has shared how he is still hesitant but is not closing doors to get vaccinated unless there is a guarantee from health agencies like the Department of Health. “Right now, hesitant pa gihapon ko nga magpabakuna pero duna koy tinguha nga unta mawala ning akong kabalaka kung naay mga garantiya gikan sa DOH nga kana bang interim facility for under observation. Pero dili gyud ko nga sirado akong kaugalingon anang mga bakuna. Kung mag-ingon ang DOH nga safe 100% siya sa persons with comorbidities and allergies. Why not?” [Right now, I am still hesitant to get vaccinated but I have this aspiration that there comes a time when all this fear will be gone if there is a guarantee from DOH to have an interim facility for those who are under observation. But I am not that close-minded in getting vaccinated. If DOH would say that it is 100% safe for persons with comorbidities and allergies. Why not?]

Vaccinating because it is mandated. One participant, who is a college student, shared one of her plans for vaccination. “Magpabakuna siguro ko ma’am kuan kay mandatory man gud sa amoa sa amoang face-to-face so magpabakuna ko pero dili pa karon.” [I think I would get vaccinated, ma’am, since it’s mandatory for our face-to-face (classes), but not now.]

Vaccinating if there’s no existing health condition. Most of the unvaccinated respondents listed their health conditions as one of the factors that hindered them from getting vaccinated. When asked about considering getting vaccinated, one participant shared that she will consider herself only if she doesn’t have a health condition, which is her heart problem. “Kung kuan wala koy gaka feel ganiha kung wala koy sakit, ma consider nako akong self since kuan man pud positive man pud ang impact sa vaccine para raman pud na siya sa atong kaayohan so if wala koy sakit ganiha, ma consider nako akong self.” [If ever I don’t have any condition, I will consider myself since the vaccines

have a positive impact and it is for our betterment so if ever, I don't have a condition, I'll consider myself.]

Considering but not yet fully decided. One participant has shared that she is considering and is still monitoring her health condition, which is her onset allergy. "Makaingon ko nga yes but dili gyud ko full ang decision nga mapaminawan nako nga taas-taas nga wala na nibalik ang akong allergy, magpa vaccine nako." [I can say that yes but my decision is not that full and I have yet to observe my condition for a long time and my allergy isn't occurring anymore, I will get vaccinated.]

Not vaccinating. One participant has shared that she will not consider herself getting vaccinated, "Dili, kay ngano? Kana man gyud number one baya sa heart...heart baya ang number one mukuan sa ato diba." [No, because why? The number one is the heart...the heart is the number one that (gets affected).]

Conclusions

This study has enabled the researchers to understand the risk perception of the COVID-19 vaccine among adults with comorbidities in Cagayan de Oro. How the vaccine is perceived by these individuals is important in discovering the approach needed for disseminating information to the public. Their perception of the vaccine influences not only themselves but also those around them. Thus, it is vital for their thoughts and opinions of the vaccine to be investigated.

Using the Health Belief Model, the study assessed the risk perception of COVID-19 vaccines among adults with comorbidities and identified factors that affect their cues to action. The results of the study indicate that the respondents had high perceived susceptibility, perceived benefits, and perceived severity. Unvaccinated respondents showed high self-efficacy for getting vaccinated. The various perceived barriers identified in this study against COVID-19 vaccination mainly include health issues, the effectiveness of the vaccine, and external influence.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Utilize a larger sample size to ensure a more comprehensive representation of the A3 population in Cagayan de Oro.
2. Consider the comorbidities of A3 respondents to determine if there is a significant difference in vaccine acceptance among individuals with varying health conditions.
3. Emphasize the importance of future research focusing on the risk perception of individuals towards different COVID-19 vaccine brands, considering the diverse range of vaccines produced in response to the pandemic.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study was conducted following ethical standards for research involving human participants. Approval was obtained from the Research Ethics Committee of Xavier University - Ateneo de Cagayan. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, and their privacy and confidentiality were strictly protected. Participants were assured of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without consequence. All data were anonymized and stored securely.

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